

A Comparative Study of the Amino-acid Composition and Nutritional Evaluation of Some Uncultivated Leguminous Seed Protein Isolates

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The albumin and globulin fraction of 4 uncultivated leguminous seeds were isolated and their amino acid composition studied. Each seed has been found to have its own pattern. Animals were fed with the protein isolates from uncultivated leguminous seeds supplemented with the limiting amino acids methionine and tryptophan. No untoward symptoms noticed and the diet proved capable of promoting growth.

IN view of the increasing demand of proteins by a growing world population several novel sources of proteins, that have hitherto not been employed in human nutrition, are now being investigated¹. Since legumes in general form one of the most important sources of proteins in Indian diet^{2,3} many leguminous plants are cultivated throughout the country. Besides these, India abounds in many uncultivated leguminous plants which grow profusely throughout the year^{4,5}. Investigations on wild leguminous seeds indicated that they were fairly good sources of proteins and suggested their possible inclusion in animal nutrition. In view of this it was considered worth while to investigate their adequacy - both qualitatively as well as quantitatively with respect to their amino acid content. The proteins were extracted and tested with and without supplementation on albino rats. The present communication describes the amino acid composition of the albumins and globulins and nutritional evaluation by animal feeding experiments of the proteins of *Cassia fistula*, *Indigofera glandulosa*, *I. hirsuta* and *I. trifoliata* seeds.

Materials and Methods: The seeds were collected and botanically identified. After cleaning, dry seeds were powdered in a grinder to 100 mesh and defatted with petroleum ether (60-80°). Albumins and globulins were isolated by following the procedure of Esh and De⁶ and their purity was tested by paper electrophoresis on an LKB 3276 equipment employing Carl Schleicher and Schull No. 2043B (120g/m², 40×410 mm) filter paper strips and buffer solutions (veronal, pH 8.6, citrate, pH 6.0; phosphate, pH 8.0 and acetate, pH 5.1).

Quantitative amino-acid analysis of the isolated seed protein hydrolyzates was carried out by paper partition chromatography on Whatman No. 1 filter paper sheets by the elution method of Rosen⁷. Tryptophan was estimated in the unhydrolyzed isolated protein samples by the method of Inglis and Leaver⁸.

Quantitative estimation of amino acids: Known volumes (2 to 3 μ l) of protein hydrolyzates were applied on Whatman No. 1 filter paper sheets (30×30 cm) in triplicate and dried well after development. One was sprayed with ninhydrin (0.1% w/v) in butanol to predetermine the location of the different amino-acids. This provided guidance and the amino-acids from the other unsprayed chromatograms were cut carefully and dropped in stoppered glass tubes, to which distilled water (1 ml), acetate-cyanide buffer (0.5 ml) and ninhydrin (0.5 ml, 0.5% w/v) in methyl cellosolve were then added. The tubes were heated in a water bath at 100° for 15 mins and diluted by the addition of a 2-propanol water mixture (5 ml, 1 to 1 v/v). The contents of the tubes were thoroughly mixed and cooled to room temperature (27°) and the colour density was measured in a colorimeter at 570 nm for all amino acids except proline, which was measured at 440 nm along with a blank and standard glycine solution. Determinations were made in triplicate, and the amount of each amino-acid was calculated in terms of glycine.

Evaluation of proteins by animal experiments: The nutritional value of the isolated purified globulin fractions of the different seed proteins is expressed as protein efficiency ratio (PER) which shows the gain in body weight in gm per gm protein intake. Net protein ratio (NPR) expressed as weight gain of the test animals in relation to the weight loss by the animals provided with nitrogen-free diet was determined by the rat growth method of Osborne *et al*⁹ as modified by Swaminathan¹⁰ on 10 albino rats per group, 4 to 5 weeks old and weighing between 40-45 gm each.

Protein efficiency ratio (PER) and net protein ratio (NPR) were calculated by the expressions as given below:

$$\text{PER} = \frac{\text{Gain in body weight in gm in 4 weeks}}{\text{Protein intake in gm in 4 weeks}}$$

$$\text{NPR} = \frac{\text{Gain in weight of experimental animals in gm in 4 weeks} + \text{loss in weight of control animals in gm in 4 weeks.}}{\text{protein intake by experimental animals in gm in 4 weeks.}}$$

Experimental diets : A diet practically nitrogen free but adequate in all other respects was prepared. It contained soluble starch (analytical reagent grade), 80 parts ; sucrose, 10 parts ; groundnut oil, 6 parts ; salt mixture^{1,2}, 2 parts and vitamin mixture, 1 part. In experimental diets starch was replaced by dietary protein at 10% level

Vitamin mixture : had the following composition per tablet in mg: Inositol, 2.2 ; choline chloride, 75 ; Niacin, 2.0 ; Riboflavin, 0.4 ; pyridoxine-HCl, 0.2 ; Thiamine-HCl 0.4 ; Calcium pantothenate, 1.2 ; Folic acid, 40 and vitamin B₁₂, 600 µg. One tablet of vitamin mixture was employed per 100 gm of the diet. Shark liver oil 5 drops per rat twice a week was administered.

Experimental diets were prepared by mixing weighed quantities in shallow aluminium pans with sufficient water, well stirred and autoclaved at 10 psi pressure for 15 mins. After cooling, weighed quantities of vitamin mixture and shark liver oil (5 drops per rat twice a week) were added to the pans, well stirred and kept in the cages.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the comparative amino-acid patterns of the four isolated seed albumins and globulins. All the seed proteins comprise 15-17 amino-acids. Globulins of seeds are complete proteins with respect to the amino acids essential for animal nutrition except methionine and tryptophan which were present in hardly traceable amount. Glutamic acid, leucine, isoleucine and aspartic acid predominate over the other

amino acids. Cysteic acid was found to be present in lesser amounts.

There is mere presence of methionine in albumin of seeds 2 and 4 and tryptophan in the seeds 1 and 4 while aspartic acid, glutamic acid, lysine, leucine-isoleucine dominate over the others.

The globulin fraction constitute the major portion (54-62%) of the seed protein^{1,2}. Thus all the four seed globulins examined could be considered as efficient source of proteins from the nutritional point of view, if supplemented with the missing essential amino-acids.

The inclusion in animal diets of the isolated albumins, although nutritionally adequate with respect to amino-acid composition, would not be economic, since their percentage in the total seed protein is too small and it did not fulfil the requirement of essential amino-acids, methionine and tryptophan.

The experimental unsupplemented protein isolates of different seeds when fed to the experimental animals failed to promote growth due to lack of tryptophan and low concentration of methionine. However, when supplemented with methionine and tryptophan they recorded protein efficiency ratio (PER) between 1.0-1.2 and net protein ratios (NPR) between 2.0-2.2 as shown in Table 2 as against 2.54 and 3.3 respectively for casein at 10% level. The PER figures are much lower than that for casein.

The obvious effect of appropriate composition of essential amino acid content in experimental diets, both qualitative and quantitative, on the appetite of experimental animals suggests a correlation between composition and growth. Although the nutritional efficiency of a protein depends almost entirely on its amino acid composition, certain other factors can not be ignored. The physiological state of the experimental

TABLE 1—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF ALBUMINS AND GLOBULINS OF SOME WILD LEGUMINOUS SEEDS

Amino-acids	(Expressed as mg glycine/100 mg proteins)							
	Albumins Seeds*				Globulins Seeds*			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
α-Alanine	1.6	1.7	1.6	1.4	3.6	3.6	4.1	3.6
Arginine	1.6	1.8	2.1	2.7	3.7	3.1	3.6	3.9
Aspartic acid	7.4	6.7	7.1	6.9	3.5	4.5	3.9	4.1
Cysteic acid	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.2	—
Glutamic acid	5.0	5.4	4.8	5.0	8.6	5.0	7.4	6.5
Glycine	1.1	0.9	1.4	1.1	2.0	2.3	1.9	2.1
Histidine	1.3	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.1
Leucine and Isoleucine	6.6	6.4	5.9	6.5	6.2	5.9	6.1	6.0
Lysine	4.2	4.5	3.8	4.4	4.0	3.0	2.7	3.2
Methionine	—	0.02	—	+	0.01	—	0.02	+
Proline	1.4	0.9	1.1	1.3	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.2
Phenylalanine	1.2	1.4	1.2	0.9	2.2	1.9	2.7	2.3
Serine	1.4	1.2	0.9	1.3	4.2	3.4	2.3	2.7
Threonine	2.5	1.8	2.7	3.1	1.0	1.1	1.4	1.4
Tryptophan	+	—	—	+	+	+	—	+
Tyrosine	0.8	1.1	0.9	1.0	1.2	0.6	0.7	0.4
Valine	1.6	1.7	1.9	1.3	2.2	2.4	2.7	2.1

Seeds* 1 = *Cassia fistula*, 2 = *Indigofera glandulosa*,

3 = *Indigofera hirsuta*, 4 = *Indigofera trifoliata*.

Optical density measured at 570 nm and for proline at 440 nm.

+ = Present, quantity not determined.

— = Absent.

TABLE 2—PROTEIN EFFICIENCY RATIO AND NET PROTEIN RATIO OF SOME UNCULTIVATED LEGUMINOUS SEED PROTEIN ISOLATES

Origin of dietary protein (seeds)	Protein intake/rat in 4 weeks (g)	Change in weight/rat in 4 weeks (g)	Protein efficiency ratio	Net protein ratio
Non-protein diet	—	-13.4±0.5	—	—
Casein	16.0±0.5	+40.6±0.8	2.54	3.3
<i>Cassia fistula</i>	8.2±0.6	- 7.9±0.2	—	—
* <i>Cassia fistula</i>	13.6±0.6	+14.8±0.4	1.08	2.07
<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	9.8±0.4	-10.6±0.2	—	—
* <i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	13.5±1.0	+16.3±0.3	1.2	2.2
<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	8.9±0.4	-10.8±0.5	—	—
* <i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	12.8±0.3	+14.8±0.4	1.16	2.2
<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>	9.0±0.4	- 8.1±0.5	—	—
* <i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>	13.4±0.7	+13.5±1.6	1.00	2.0

*Supplemented with L-methionine (0.15 per cent) and L-tryptophan (0.20 per cent). Dietary protein was at 10 per cent level.

animals, for example, as well as the consequent uncontrollable changes in the rate of availability of amino-acids to them are factors which vary by appreciable margins and significantly affect the nutritional efficiency of proteins.

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